

Algorithmic Masculinity: Encounters with the Manosphere

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1. How is masculinity understood, negotiated and performed (by humans and non-humans) on social media platforms today?

My research explores how the algorithmic personalisation of information feeds on social media platforms co-constitutes understandings of masculinity among young cis men, living in Sweden. I focus on how they encounter, engage with and interpret content that promotes essentialist, heteronormative and misogynistic ideals of masculinity – on Instagram, TikTok, YouTube and Snapchat. These kinds of ideals circulate intensely within the ‘manosphere’, a global online movement comprising groups such as Men’s Rights Activists, Pick-Up Artists, Red Pillers, MGTOW and Incels (Gottzén, 2022; Han & Yin 2023; Johanssen 2022; Schmitz & Kazayak 2016) but are amplified more broadly through the commercial logic of today’s digital information infrastructure (Ging, Bakers & Andreasen 2024; Thomas & Balint 2022).

The aim of this thesis is to gain a nuanced understanding of how young cis men’s masculine identities are understood, negotiated and performed (by humans and non-humans) at the intersection of their information activities on social media platforms, the manosphere and the techno-commercial conditions of the digital information infrastructure. The study is guided by the following research questions: What ideals of masculinity do young cis men encounter online? How does the digital information infrastructure enable and/or limit these encounters? How do young cis men’s information activities on social media platforms enable and/or limit these encounters? How do young cis men negotiate their masculine identities in relation to the algorithmic personalisation of their information feeds and the ideals of masculinity they encounter therein?

The methodology combines infrastructural go-alongs and interviews in which the participants use and reflect on their information feeds in real time. Metadata and platform policies are analysed to understand how the materiality of the infrastructure influences these processes. Theoretically, the project draws on socio-material theory, in particular Karen Barad’s concepts, and Judith Butler’s theory of gender performativity.

Preliminary results dealing with the search practises of young men will be presented on the poster. This includes how they use personalised information feeds on social media platforms instead of traditional search engines in their everyday lives and how their search practises take shape in the form of an algorithmic dance.

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